

KJHS
Kaduna Journal of
Historical
Studies

VOL 12 NUMBER 1, 2021

ISSN: 2141 - 1832

**A Publication of the Department of History,
Kaduna State University, Kaduna - Nigeria**

KJHS

Kaduna Journal of Historical Studies

Volume 12 Number 1, 2021

ISSN: 2141-1832

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- The submission which should contain the title page should also contain professional details of the author(s): name(s), contact address and institutional/organizational affiliation all in the first page.
- Each paper should be accompanied with an abstract. Quotation exceeding 40 words should be indented in 10 font size and single-spaced.
- Submissions should adopt the Sixteenth Edition of the Chicago Manual of Style for referencing.

Note: Opinions expressed in the journal are neither those of the Department of History, the Editorial members nor that of Kaduna State University, but are surely that of the authors.

Editorial Note

Kaduna Journal of Historical Studies (KJHS) is a journal of the Department of History, Kaduna State University that publishes well researched articles, book reviews, review articles and scholarly opinions from scholars, researchers, policy makers and opinion molders among others, on a wide range of topics within the disciplines of humanities; dealing with issues that augments knowledge and ideas, whose lessons would provide the path towards scholarship development, peace, harmony, and security in Nigeria, Africa and the world.

KJHS, which is peer-reviewed is also fully referenced and seeks to promote deeper understanding of issues in Nigeria, Africa and the world through scholarly researches and exchange of knowledge useful to students, researchers, academics, policy makers and opinion molders as well as enriching the general readers. KJHS editorial policy is neither committed to any constricted ideological prism nor political viewpoint. Instead, it recognizes that a wide range of multi-disciplinary approaches are fundamental in understanding a wide range of issues surrounding the respective disciplines of history in particular and the humanities in general. It equally appreciates that opposing viewpoints and ideologies, which have shaped and are still shaping the understanding/misunderstanding of historical issues are legitimate in academic discourses. This is one of our responsibilities in a university; and as professional historians, our aim is the universalization of knowledge and cross-pollination of ideas for development and human progress.

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The Misunderstood Concepts of Jihad and Crusade: What it means for State and Global Politics in the 21st Century

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Abstract

The thrust of this paper is to examine contemporary definitions of the Jihad from Islam and the Crusade from Christianity, as well as, show how the interpretations of these concepts affect state and global politics. Using information obtained from extensive library research, internet resources, and oral interviews (anonymous informants), the paper shows that, with very few exceptions, the misconceptions of Jihad and Crusade have been deliberately sponsored and promoted for political gains. This inhuman act has affected state and global politics negatively, resulting in recurring religious instigated conflicts, insecurity, and destruction of lives and properties. The paper concludes that, for Nation-States to achieve sustained peace, religious tolerance must be promoted, especially, at the grassroots level (rural areas). The committee of Nations must take cognizance of (and never neglect and/or abuse) the important role played by religion in state and global politics. Hence, the concepts of Jihad and Crusade should be redefined to concur with the tenets of affiliated religion.

Introduction

The Crusade and Jihad are unarguably among the most subtle, misunderstood, misinterpreted and manipulated concepts of the 21st century. This is further exacerbated by conscious and deliberate manipulation of the broad nature and/or sensitivity of the concepts by state and non-state sponsored individuals and organisations for selfish political gains. As such, the literal, contextual, and figurative meanings of the terms (Crusade and Jihad) have been abysmally misinterpreted, exploited, and utilized to promote and facilitate global

political instability via incitement of the rural/local populace and encouragement of unhealthy ethno-religious rivalry, conflict and violent.

Ironically, the concepts are affiliated to two of the world's most popular monotheist religions (Christianity and Islam). Historically, the two religions are related, being that their adherents claim to be descendants of the patriarch Abraham/Ibrahim one of the major prophets of God (according to the Holy Books) renowned to have promoted the concept of monotheism in Mesopotamia and Palestine. The concept of Jihad may be traced to the official declaration of the religion of Islam by Prophet Mohammad (PBUH) in Mecca, Arabia in the 7th century C.E. on the other hand; Crusade in Christianity is linked to the series of campaigns by European Christians in Palestine against the Muslims in the middle ages. In a sense, the Jihad was born alongside the religion of Islam and considered an obligation that must be adhered to by all true Muslims. The Crusade on its part was a 'child of necessity' adopted by European Christians to reclaim Christian lands in the Middle Ages.

This paper particularly became necessary as a result of the unpleasant consequences of the misconception and manipulation of the concepts of Crusade and Jihad on state and global politics in the 21st century, as well as the long term effects on the future generation of humanity if not permanently addressed. Hence, the findings of the study are intended to assist stakeholders proffer lasting solutions to religious related conflicts (political instability) at the state and global levels.

The paper is divided into ten sections. The sections are abstract, introduction, Christianity and the concept of Crusade, The concept of Jihad from Islam, The emergence of Religious Ideological, Hate and Militant Movements/Institutions, Islamic Extremist Ideological and/or Militant Movements, Christian Ideological, Hate and Militant Movements/Institutions, Effects of the Misinterpretation and Manipulation of the concepts of Crusade and Jihad on State and Global Politics, Conclusion, and Bibliography.

Christianity and the Concept of Crusade

According to the Holy Bible, the term 'Christian' was first used in the city of 'Antioch' to refer to the disciples and/or followers of Jesus Christ (Act 11:26). The religion of Christianity itself is build upon the teachings of Jesus Christ and the belief that he is the son of God. The pillar of the faith is anchored on the belief that Jesus Christ died and

resurrected so that his followers and adherents of the Christian faith can have eternal life.

Christianity as a distinct religious belief may be traced to an encounter between the archangel Gabriel and a young virgin descendant of Abraham whose name was Mary. The angel revealed to Mary that she will be conceived by the Holy Spirit and bear a child (a son) before she knew any man. This revelation eventually came to pass and Mary conceived and bore a son, and the child was named Jesus. At age thirty, Jesus began to promote a distinct form of monotheism. He taught that there was only one God, and that he (Jesus) was the Son of God. He also taught about the gentility, love and forgiving nature of God. His intriguing teachings won him many followers (among the Jews and Gentile) and brought him at loggerheads with the religious leaders of the Jews (the Scribes and Pharisees). He was subsequently crucified (nailed to a stake/cross) by the Roman authorities who were eager to please and as such retain the support of the Jewish leaders. Upon his death and resurrection (according to his followers) his disciples spread his teachings throughout the Roman Empire and beyond.

The word Crusade was derived from the word crucifixion (the act of killing somebody by fastening them to a wooden cross). The Cross is the symbol of the Christian faith and Church. In contemporary times, the term is defined in two ways, depending on how it is written. When written with its initial in capital letter 'Crusade', it is mostly used in reference to and/or means any military expedition taken by the Christians against non-Christians, especially the 11th, 12th, and 13th century military campaigns by Christians of Europe for the recovery of the Holy land from the Muslims. In its other sense, the word when written with its initial in small letter 'crusade', it means a long determined effort to achieve something believed to be right, or to stop something believed to be wrong.

The First Crusade (1096-1099) was instigated by Emperor Alexius I of Byzantine (the eastern half of the former Roman Empire), and sanctioned by Pope Urban II of the Roman Catholic Church. The European Christian religious leaders and Monarchs/Aristocrats that called for the Crusades justified their actions on the basis of the concept of "Just War". Notable leaders of the Crusaders in the first European Christian Crusade included Raymond of Saint-Gilles, Godfrey of Bouillon, Hugh of Vermandois, and Bohemond of Taranto. The First Crusade ended with the Christians occupation of Jerusalem in mid-July, 1099, and has been adjudged the most successful of the major Crusades.

The Second Crusade (1147-1149) was led by King Louis vii of France and King Conrad of Germany. The Crusaders were decisively defeated by a combined Muslim forces led by the leaders of Damascus and Mosul. The Third Crusade (1187-1192) was led by Emperor Frederick Barbarossa, King Philip ii of France, and King Richard i of England. The campaign ended with a peace treaty signed by King Richard and Salahadin. The peace treaty re-established the kingdom of Jerusalem (without the city of Jerusalem). The Fourth Crusade was diverted and ended with the devastating destruction of Constantinople, the capital of Byzantine. Although, a couple of military campaigns (Crusades) were carried out after the fourth Crusade, their impacts were of little historical significance.

In some Christian denominations in recent times, the word crusade has been refined and redefined to mean mass gathering of Christian faithful for the purpose of recommitment to the teachings of Jesus Christ. It has also been used to mean evangelism and/or deliberate attempts to win more converts to the Christian faith. However, the deliberate attempts by some state and non-state actors to manipulate the concept (crusade) for individualistic political gains still persist.

The Concept of Jihad From Islam

Islam is an offshoot of an Arabic word for peace. Hence, Islam has been referred to as a religion of peace. The rise of Islam began with a series of revelations to Prophet Mohammed (PBUH) between 611 A.D. and 632 A.D. in Mecca and Medina (in the present day Kingdom of Saudi Arabia). Adherents of Islam are called Muslims, and the Qu'ran meaning 'Recite' (the first word revealed to the Prophet) is the Holy Book of the Muslims. Prophet Mohammed (PBUH) was a 'thinker' and born 'reformer'. He won many followers to his side through preaching and conquered many lands in a number of peaceful and military campaigns referred to as Jihad (Internal struggle and/or Holy War). He died in 632 A.D. after which His followers continued with the ideologies of the Jihad conquering many lands in the Middle East, South East Asia, North Africa, and winning new converts. Islam is not just a religion but a culture. It is a way of life, and as such, often combines elements of social, economic and political undertones.

According to Shaykh Muhammad Hisham Kabbani and Shaykh Seraj Hendricks, the Arabic word Jihad often translated as 'holy war' actually means struggling or striving in its purely linguistic sense. They argued further, that contrary to the populist definition of jihad as 'holy war', the Arabic word for war is 'al-harb'. Hence, Jihad is neither a violent concept nor is the term a declaration of war against

other monotheist religions (Christianity and Judaism) that worship the same God.

The Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary (8th edition, 2010:804) puts forward two definitions for Jihad. Firstly it refers to Jihad as a spiritual struggle within a Muslim to stop breaking religious or moral laws. It also refers to Jihad as a holy war fought by Muslims to defend Islam. It is this latter interpretation that political desperadoes capitalize on to incite ethno-political conflicts for egocentric political gains. Shaykhs Kibbani and Seraj also warned that in coming to terms with the concept of Jihad, context and circumstance of the Qur'anic revelation and Hadith should be taken into consideration. Unfortunately, this particular aspect has been largely ignored in the contemporary teachings of Islam by extremist Islamic scholars and their sponsors.

The Jihad which was and still is instrumental to the dissemination of the message of the Prophet and internationalisation of Islam has been interpreted and conceptualized in a number of ways. To some Islamic Scholars, (especially the modernists' school of Islamic thought) the Jihad is a Non-Violent and/or Peaceful Movement intended to persuade the non-believers and the misled to the true Religion of God by words and work of the heart, tongue, and hand. The proponents of this school of thought argue that since Islam is a religion of peace, there was no basis for the application of force and/or use of violence. They opine that the Prophets first converts willingly accepted Islam and believed the words of the Prophet (Jihad of the heart, tongue and hand). One who is conversant with the Islamic history of Sub-Saharan Africa may agree with the modernist Islamic school of thought. In a sense, it was through persuasions and exemplary conducts that the Arab merchants and scholars of North Africa won most of their permanent converts in the lands south of the Sahara Desert and beyond.

The hardliner Conservatives however insist that the Jihad is a Holy war by Sword/compulsion (Jihad of the Sword). These hardliners argue that Medina and Mecca were forcefully subdued at the edge of the sword, in very much the same way that most parts of the Middle East and North Africa were brought to submission to Islam. It is interesting to note however, that in most of the lands where the people were forced to convert to Islam, many of such conversions were temporal and/or passive, for as soon as the leader of the Jihad Movement that forcefully converted them died, majority of the converts either reverted back to their former beliefs or practiced passive Islam.

A third school of Islamic scholars who we will refer to as the Moderates argue that the Jihad entails both the use of words of the mouth and application of force when and where necessary. This school of thought however insist on a balanced moderation in the use of persuasion and the application of force. It maintains that it is only in situations where the use of persuasion fails that force should be resorted to as a last resort. It corroborates its position with the argument that the Prophet initially employed peaceful approaches to convince the people of Mecca and Medina, and that it was after a section of the people refused to listen to his message and even sort after his life that force was applied. Some of the West Africa Jihads featured the propositions of the Islamic moderates' school of thought. For instance, Uthman dan Fodio (the leader of the 1804 Jihads in Hausa land) preached reformation of the Hausa states; it was after the Hausa conservative ruling elites refused to restructure their domains that force was used to enforce reforms and to alter the status quo.

The Emergence of Religious Ideological, Hate and Militant Movements/Institutions

The manipulation of religion, misinformation and promotion of religious intolerance provides fertile breeding grounds for insurgency, terrorism, ethno-religious politics, conflict and violence. While some observers view support for fundamentalism and extremism as a natural reaction by people who are overwhelmed by massive change and desire to seek security in long valued traditions. Others however, are quick to point out that the continuous growth of religious fundamentalism in Africa, Asia, and the Middle East will deepen mistrust and harden prejudices at a time when efforts towards peace are moving forward. Unfortunately, very little or no attention has been given to the misunderstood concepts of Crusade and Jihad from Christianity and Islam. And as such, global policy makers fail to take cognizance of the effects that the interpretations of these concepts have on state and global politics.

A brief overview of the political history Africa, Asia, and the Middle East in the twentieth and twenty first century shows that both regions have remained important focal point for international discuss. Their vast mineral wealth (especially crude oil in Africa and the Middle East) and population (manpower and markets) have been a source of investment attraction as well as the bane of conflict between western multinational corporations (often supported by their home governments) and the impoverished countries of Africa, Asia, and the Middle East. The influx of western investors and western

culture into these regions, and the subsequent trend of globalization are sometimes perceived as threats to established social, economic and political cultures of the people which must be resisted. Resistant to economic exploitation and clash of cultures soon took on a religious dimension.

Varying anti-western religious ideological, hate and militant movements/organisations soon emerged and enjoyed the support of majority of the people at the early stages of their formation. At first the people saw nothing wrong in supporting these so-called 'Liberation Movements' whose aims and objectives were in line with the political, moral and religious aspirations of the people. The people these regions (Africa, Asia, and the Middle East) very much sought to preserve their sovereignty, stop exploitation and halt the diffusion of western ideas perceived to be incompatible with established indigenous cultures. However, the transformation of many of the hitherto tagged liberation movements into religious extremist and militant movements, the same people (who had hitherto supported them and had been on tenterhooks over the outcome of their liberation struggles) began to cast aspersions on their terrifying and destructive modus operandi. Soon these religious militant extremist movements with origins in Africa, Asia, the Middle East, and the Americas soon found their way to other parts of the globe.

Christian Ideological, Hate and Militant Movements/Institutions

The misconceptions of the tenets of Christianity have taken up different dimensions over the years. Christian ideological Movements and/or institutions like the Inquisition, Radical Christianity, Christian fundamentalism, Christian extremism, Christian hate groups, etc., have been wrongly associated with the concept of crusade. That is because some leaders and members of these movements claim to carry out different aspects of the crusade either peacefully or violently. However, while Islamic extremist have continued to unleashed acts of terror via organised group networks and/or cells, the manifestation of acts of terrorism by Christian fanatics have gradually shifted from organised group networks to isolated cases of solo acts of terrorism perpetrated by individuals members of Christian hate movements. Suffice it to say that solo acts of terrorism carried out by brainwashed individuals is often more difficult to detect, track, and prevent from happening. It is easier for security agents to track, monitor and follow activities of religious groups/movements which must meet at particular meeting points, have a hierarchy of leaders that are easily

identified, and possess traceable assets. These may not always be the case for solo religious terrorist operating independently.

Many Christian ideological, hate and militant movements have appeared and disappeared since the Crusades of the 11th, 12th, and 13th century. Among these movements was the Inquisition (often referred to as an institution of the Papacy and secular governments of Europe) which started in France in the 12th century. From France the Inquisition spread to other parts of Europe, and lasted for about six centuries before it was eventually ended in the 19th century. The Inquisition was sanctioned by the papacy, while punishments were meted out by secular government authorities. Allegedly established to fight heresy within the Catholic Church, many Jews and Muslims were forcefully converted, prosecuted and executed. In a sense, the Inquisition was a modified form of Crusade (to salvage Christianity from alleged heresy and non-Christians); even though some scholars insist that the Inquisition was an institution. Either ways, the hard truth is that the Inquisition was a Catholic hate initiative aimed at converting, prosecuting and executing perceived enemies of the Catholic Papacy and its practices.

The God Worshipping Society which established the Taiping Heavenly Kingdom (1850-1864) was a fusion of Christianity, Taoism, Confucianism, and Millenarianism. This syncretised model of Christianity which manipulated and misinterpreted the tenets of the Christian faith was founded by Hong Xiuquan and his cohorts as means of achieving their political ambitions during the Manchu led Qing dynasty in China. Upon failing the imperial civil service qualification examination for a fourth time, Hong claimed that he had gone through a transcendental experience during which certain visions were shown to him. Subsequently, he presumed that the content of some Christian pamphlets (distributed by some European missionaries) which content he not taking serious initially provided meanings to his visions. Based on his personal interpretation of the Christian tracts, Hong claimed to be the second born son of God and a younger brother of Jesus Christ. After he had garnered reasonable support and followers made up of poor village dwellers, pirate groups, bandits, and deserters, Hong proclaimed himself ruler of the Taiping Heavenly Kingdom. He lived in luxury and kept many women in his inner chambers. The violent military campaigns carried out by his followers against the Qing dynasty have been variously described by scholars as the Taiping Rebellion, Taiping civil war, or the Taiping revolution. The conflict claimed millions of lives and has been termed one of the most violent events of the 19th century.

Lord's Resistance Army (LRA) initially known as the United Holy Salvation Army and Uganda Christian Army Movement was founded by Joseph Koni (a self claimed prophet) in 1987. Koni and his lieutenants claimed that part of the aim of the movement was to establish a multi-party democracy that will rule Uganda according to the Biblical Ten Commandments. Subsequently, the activities of the LRA spanned across national borders in Africa. The movement carried out guerrilla warfare in Uganda, South Sudan, Central African Republic, and the Democratic Republic of Congo, often with many civilian casualties. Joseph Koni's manipulation of the Christian religion and misinformation of the populace led his volatile admirers to believe that his actions were sanctioned by God Almighty, and that he was fighting a Just War, at least at the formation stages of the LRA. In reality however, Koni had a hidden agenda, which was the quest for political power. The LRA has been accused of committing war atrocities like forceful recruitment of child soldiers, human rights violation, mutilation, child sex slavery, to name but a few. Unfortunately, the activities of the LRA were often supported by state and non-state actors (governments and non-government agencies) of the various countries it operated i.e. Sudan and the Democratic Republic of Congo.

Misinformed by the teachings of leaders of some Christian Hate groups, members of such groups embarked on what may be best described as solo Crusades (which in some cases were not sanctioned by leaders of their respective movements). The aim of these solo crusades carried out by members of these hate groups was and is still to salvage the Christian faith from what they perceive as planned suppression of Christianity by non-Christians (Jews and Muslims), heresy (abortion sanctioned by state authorities), relegation of the supremacy of the white race, and other imagined actions that threaten their beliefs. There have been series of anti-Semitic, anti-Islamic, anti-gay, and white supremacist attacks in recent times. The most recent being the 15th March, 2019 Christchurch shootings at the Al Noor Mosque and Linwood Islamic Centre in New Zealand in which at least fifty (50) persons were killed. The main suspect Brenton Harrison Terrant, a twenty eight years old Australian man was allegedly reported to have been influenced by white supremacy and anti-Islamic ideologies according to media reports. However, policy makers and journalist failed to understand (choose not to accept and report) is that the suspect was also misinformed about the concept of Crusade in Christianity, and as such, had carried out a solo crusade in his own rights (from his own perspective/point of view).

Islamic Extremist Ideological and Militant Movements/Institutions
 In Islamic circles, the activities of Islamic ideological and militant groups have been generally referred to as the *Takfiri* Movement. In Islamic law, *takfir* or *takfeer* refers to the practice of excommunication, one Muslim declaring another Muslim as *kafir* (infidel). The act which precipitates *takfir* is termed the *mukaffir*. A *takfiri* is a Sunni Muslim who accuses another Muslim (or an adherent of another Abrahamic faith) of apostasy. The accusation itself is called *takfir*, derived from the word *kafir* (unbeliever), and is described as when "one who is, or claims to be, a Muslim is declared impure. *Takfir* is used in the modern era for sanctioning violence against leaders of Islamic states who are deemed insufficiently religious. It has become a central ideology of militant groups such as those in Egypt, which reflect the ideas of Sayyid Qutb, Mawdudi, Ibn Taymiyya, and Ibn Kathir. Mainstream Muslims and moderate Islamic groups reject the concept as a doctrinal deviation. Islamic clerics such as Hassan al-Hudaybi (d. 1997) and Yusuf al-Qaradawi reject *takfir* as un-Islamic and marked by bigotry and zealotry. The *Takfiri* Islamist has been described as a Sunni Muslim sect (debatable though), Holy warriors who "legitimately" slaughtered other Muslims because they deemed them no longer Muslims but *kuffar*, infidels, who may be killed in conflict.

The activities of these Islamic groups and their ideologies influenced the formation of extremist groups in Africa, Asia, the Middle East, and other regions of the world. Al-Quaeda, Hezbollah, Islamic State Movement (ISIS), *Al Shabab* and *Jama'atu Ahlis Sunna Lidda'awati wal-Jihad* (*Boko Haram*) are just a few out of many such groups. ISIS has claimed responsibility for many fatal bomb attacks across the globe. *Al Shabab* is active in the horn of Africa and East Africa (Somalia, Ethiopia, and Kenya), and *Boko Haram* is active in West Africa and neighbouring sub-regions (Nigeria, Cameroun, Chad, Niger, etc.). As has been stated earlier, the initial reactions and reflections of majority of the people supported the activities of these groups when their aims were perceived as genuinely anti-western. However, as many of the groups gradually adopted violent religious ideologies and terrorist strategies the people began to question the sincerity of their motives.

Effects of the Misinterpretation and Manipulation of the Concepts of Crusade and Jihad on State and Global Politics

A notable effect of the misinterpretation of the concepts of Crusade and Jihad from Christianity and Islam on state and global politics is Global wide Human Rights Violation and Discrimination based on religious affiliation. Discrimination refers to any form of inhuman

treatment meted out to a person or group of persons on the basis of personality and/or believe(s). Amnesty International posits that every human being should be treated equally, irrespective of social, economic, and political status in society. It goes on to chide some governments that consolidate their grip on power by openly justifying discrimination and human rights abuses in the name of "morality", religion or ideology'.

The violent activities of religious ideological and militant movements have had some negative effects on the fundamental human rights of the people of Africa, Asia, the Middle East, and the world. Consistent attacks on Churches and Mosques have infringed the rights of freedom of worship, movement and expression. As many people in the affected regions no longer find it safe to move freely or express themselves without fears of attacks. The Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights reports that on a daily basis, members of religious or belief communities face discrimination based on their religion or belief. They are unduly prevented from enjoying their civil, cultural, economic, political, and social rights. As such, members of the victimized religions are denied access to public education, health services, and public positions. In extreme cases, some of them are arrested, detained, or killed without following due processes, for the single crime of belonging to a particular religion.

Frequent attacks on schools by the religious militant groups have led to closure of schools in the worst affected regions, thereby interrupting the academic activities of students in the affected areas. There have also been reports of human right abuses, sex slavery. In this case, both the religious affiliated terrorist movements and the State security agencies have been indicted of these offences. Innocent citizens have been unlawfully arrested, tortured and detained by security operatives without trials for merely suspected to be sympathetic to the religious affiliated terrorist movements. Also, these religious terrorist movements have been reported to use captured girls and women as sex slaves. Both public and private infrastructures have not been spared as telecommunication facilities, private and government buildings, markets, Dams, pipe lines, etc., have been attacked and destroyed.

Unsustainable Economic Development, Growth and increased Poverty margins along religious lines is another notable effect of the misunderstood concepts of Crusade and Jihad on state and global politics. According to the International Labour Organisation (ILO), unsustainable economic development, growth and increased poverty are among the direct consequences of social, economic, and political

discrimination on state and global scale. Many industries in the worst affected regions in Africa and the Middle East have either had to relocate or wind up for fear of possible attacks or kidnap of staff. More so, foreign and local investors have been scared away from investing in the affected areas. This has led to increase unemployment, underemployment and mass rural-urban migration, which is not in the interest and/or favourable to state, sub-regional, regional and global economies.

A direct consequence of discrimination, unsustainable economic development and growth is increased national, regional and global poverty. World Bank reports that in 2015, more than half of the world's extremely poor people lived in sub-Saharan Africa. It went on to state that the majority of the global poor that lived in rural areas were poorly educated, employed in the agricultural sector, and under 18 years of age. The report showed that these extremely poor people lived in fragile countries and in the most remote areas where access to critical services remained elusive to them. This observation was further corroborated by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) human development reports on the 2018 global multidimensional poverty index (MPI). The report showed Sub-Saharan Africa (560,000,000) and South Asia (546,000,000) as the leading regions housing the world's poorest population. Suffice it to be said that with such large number of extremely poor population, these regions became vulnerable to all manners of criminality, religious intolerance, and ethno-religious conflicts. These precedents for state and global political instability are sometimes instigated by political despots for selfish political gains.

Conclusion

The projections and/or reports of concerned globally respected specialized institutions like the ILO, OHCHR, AI, UNDP, and the World Bank on discrimination, unsustainable economic development, growth and increased poverty (consequences of misconception, misinterpretation, misinformation, manipulation of basic religious tenets i.e. the concepts of Crusade and Jihad on state and global politics) do not spell a doomed and/or gloomy future for states in the most affected regions. Rather, there seems to be light at the end of the tunnel if the right steps and measures are taken on time and in the right direction. These steps should start by deliberate efforts to identify the root cause of the problem, organisation of enlightenment programmes at the grassroots levels, and correction of erroneous misconceptions of essential social, economic, and political concepts.

The word Islam in Arabic is derived from the causative form of the simple root "*Salam*" meaning "peace", thus, the religion of peace. Islam thus is and should remain a religion of peace. The same should be the case with Christianity. Jesus Christ and Prophet Mohammed (SAW) preached love, kindness, and peaceful co-existence with fellow human beings. Neither of them supported the use of force and/or violence in achieving religious goals. Furthermore, if God had never meant the earth to be civilized, He would not have provided it with rich material and human resources or endowed man with complex reasoning faculties to utilize these resources for his survival. Therefore, not all aspects of the western and/or modern civilization are evil. There are aspects of the western and/or modern ideas that are good and can be beneficial to Christians and Muslims alike. A Muslim should be able to discern and or sift what is good from what is bad in the western culture, likewise a Christian. Hence, policy makers at the state, sub-regional, regional, and global levels should as a matter of urgency organise periodical rural area and/or grassroots level enlightenment campaigns via seminars, workshops, conferences to promote and facilitate a change of individual perceptions and perspectives on the concepts of Crusade and Jihad from Christianity and Islam

More so, Yusuf Bala Usman (The Manipulation of Religion in Nigeria, 2014:160) observed that most religious related violence was and is still instigated by political desperadoes for selfish political gains. He stated further that some state and non-state actors have repeatedly sponsored some of the more violent religious ideological, hate, and militant movements/institutions in the world. These observations notwithstanding, the call is for religious movements/institutions to ignore the worldly offers of some shameless and faceless political power seekers, emulate Jesus Christ and Prophet Mohammed (PBUH) and double their efforts by reaching out to the public and driving home their messages through persuasive and peaceful ways. Christianity and Islam have always been primary religions for active and responsible persons and religious belief systems for people whose attitudes are constructive. Most importantly, the concepts of Crusade and Jihad from Christianity and Islam should be refined and redefined all state and non-state policy makers to concur with the original tenets of affiliated religions for a more peaceful and prosperous world.

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**A Publication of the Department of History,
Kaduna State University, Kaduna - Nigeria**